

SIMULTANEOUS ELECTRO-MECHANICAL TESTING OF A STRUCTURAL BATTERY

T.E. Tay^{1*}, K. Raju¹, V.B.C. Tan¹

¹ Department of Mechanical Engineering, National University of Singapore, Singapore

*Corresponding author: mpetayte@nus.edu.sg

Keywords: 3-point bend test, structural battery composites, concurrent electrochemical-mechanical testing, composite current collectors

ABSTRACT

Structural batteries [1] combine structural load bearing capabilities with electrochemical functionalities. In order to achieve this dual purpose, the battery must be able to function electrically while sustaining mechanical loads. This work presents a simultaneous electromechanical (SEM) testing of a structural battery pouch cell under three-point flexural load while electrochemical testing. An important component is the current collectors, which are expected to function as conveyors of the electric current generated by the battery's electrochemical reactions, as well as possessing mechanical stiffness. This presentation also describes the selection of carbon fiber-based collectors considering the tensile properties and electrical resistivity of the fabricated current collectors. Current collectors fabricated using 5% PVDF (Polyvinylidene Fluoride) as the polymer matrix is used to fabricate PEO solid electrolyte based structural battery pouch cells employing Lithium Iron Phosphate (LFP) cathode and Lithium Titanium Oxide (LTO) anode, with a cellulose separator. In addition to conventional electrochemical testing of pouch cells, SEM tests are carried out to demonstrate the working of the cell under mechanical load and demonstrate the effect of mechanical loads on electrochemical performance. It is hoped that this and similar SEM tests will contribute to the development of eventual standards for the evaluation of structural batteries.

1 INTRODUCTION

Structural batteries are multi-functional material systems designed to store electro-chemical energy while serving as structural load bearing members of a system such as an electric vehicle. Structural batteries are a potential solution to improve drive range of electric vehicles, drones, etc. According to a study [2], the drive range of an electric car may be increased by 70% with the introduction of structural batteries while maintaining the weight of a vehicle.

Most structural battery prototypes published today employ liquid [3,4] or bicontinuous electrolytes [5–7]. Bicontinuous electrolytes suffer from the ionic conducting liquid phase squeezed out under certain loading conditions such as compression, as reported by Tavano *et al* [8]. In this work, a Polyethylene Oxide (PEO) based solid electrolyte [9] is used for developing the structural batteries. Carbon fibre is widely employed as an electrode in many prototypes and when carbon fibre is employed as an electrode, issues such as the high first cycle capacity loss make it difficult to balance charge capacity of the electrodes which is essential to fabricate full cells. In this work, carbon fibre is employed only as a current collector and Lithium Titanium Oxide (LTO) is used as the anode with Lithium Iron Phosphate (LFP) as the cathode.

Most structural battery research do not report the effect of mechanical loads on electrochemical cycling. This work aims to illustrate the importance of demonstrating the working and quantifying the effect of mechanical loads of structural battery prototypes. First, a suitable current collector is developed and selected for fabricating structural battery pouch cells with PEO based solid electrolyte and LFP and LTO electrodes. The developed prototype is tested in bending to demonstrate the effect of flexural loads on the electrochemical performance of the pouch cell.

2 METHODOLOGY

The development of current collectors by optimizing for the amounts of PVDF and electrically conductive carbon nanotubes (CNT) are discussed in section 2.1. The pouch cell fabrication and electrochemical testing is discussed in section 2.2. The simultaneous flexural and electrochemical testing of the pouch cells is reported in section 2.3

2.1 Current collector fabrication and testing

The carbon fibre based current collectors are fabricated from T300 unidirectional (UD) carbon fibres. The current collector needs to efficiently conduct current and bear loads. In this work since loose carbon fibres are not efficient in bearing various loads, a polymer matrix Polyvinylidene Fluoride (PVDF) is used to develop current collectors in this work termed as CF-PVDF current collectors. PVDF is used since it is a commonly used binder in battery electrode slurries, and known to not have any adverse side-reactions with other chemicals used in battery fabrication. However, PVDF is an insulator, so the quantity of the PVDF deposited must be optimized. Similarly, carbon nanotube suspensions (TUBALL™) used for improving battery electrode slurries are also applied on bare T300 carbon fibres to fabricate CF-CNT current collectors. The different current collectors fabricated are listed in Table 1.

Table 1: Fabricated composite current collectors

Materials	Sample label
pure Carbon fiber	CF
CF-PVDF made with 1%PVDF-DMF (Dimethylformamide) solution	1%CF-PVDF
CF-PVDF made with 5%PVDF-NMP (N-Methyl-2-Pyrrolidone) solution	5%CF-PVDF
CF-CNT coated twice	CF-CNT-2c
CF-CNT coated once	CF-CNT-1c
CF-CNT coated once and deposited PVDF	CF-CNT-PVDF

The various carbon fibre current collectors were fabricated and tested for their resistance and tensile behaviour as shown in the flowchart in Figure 1 below. The fabrication, testing methods and the development of current collectors are reported in more detail in [10]. The results of the resistance and tensile measurements are summarised in section 3.1 to guide the selection of the current collector.

Figure 1: Current Collector development workflow

2.2 Pouch cell fabrication and testing

The LFP and LTO slurries and the PEO slurries are prepared as per the recipes in appendices A1 and A2 respectively. Once the slurries and the electrolyte are prepared, a battery can be fabricated with any of the current collectors described above. In this work, the 5% CF-PVDF current collector was used to fabricate pouch cells and carry out the simultaneous testing of electrochemical and mechanical loads since it exhibited relatively good electrical conductivity, tensile properties and is suitable for pouch cell fabrication, as explained later in section 3.1. Two current collectors (cut to 30-40 mm in length and 10-15mm width) are then coated with LFP and LTO slurries as shown in the leftmost images in Figure 2 and dried in an oven. A cellulose separator is coated with the PEO electrolyte on both sides and dried in an oven. The anode, the cellulose separator infused with the PEO electrolyte and cathode are assembled and placed in a pouch cell film which is partially sealed and vacuum dried at 80°C overnight to remove moisture. The dried pouch cell is then vacuum sealed. The whole fabrication procedure is shown in Figure 2.

Figure 2: Pouch cell fabrication

The fabricated pouch cell was electrochemically tested at constant current magnitudes corresponding to rates of 0.1C and 0.2C at 60°C. The pouch cells were charged and discharged between 1 and 2.5V. The high temperature electrochemical performance is also compared to the cell's electrochemical performance at room temperature.

2.3 Simultaneous Electro-Mechanical (SEM) testing

Most research work [3–7,11] follows a sequential workflow of designing structural batteries, demonstrating the electrochemical performance of the battery and evaluate the mechanical behaviour (with tensile testing) of the structural battery as shown in Figure 3(c). The demonstration of electrochemical and mechanical performance in isolation (isolated multifunctionality) does not quantify and determine the electrochemical performance of the structural battery under mechanical loads (simultaneous multi-functionality). If structural batteries are to be practically realized, simultaneous electro-mechanical tests as shown in the flowchart in Figure 3(d) are essential to demonstrate that the structural battery can operate under mechanical loads. However simultaneous tests are challenging since the time scales involved in the electrochemical tests (at low charging currents) are long compared to time scales of typical mechanical tests and the lack of test standards.

This work aims to demonstrate the effect of mechanical three-point bend loads on electrochemical performance [12] and that the fabricated structural battery prototype continued operating after the test. The simultaneous electro-mechanical (SEM) testing of the cell was carried out with a set-up shown in Figure 3(a). The set-up comprises a universal testing machine Instron 5848 and NEWARE battery tester. The cell was loaded to an extent such that the pouch cell does not mechanically fail (indicated by a load drop) or electrically short to demonstrate the operation of the cell under load. The loading pin was held at the constant cross head displacement during the SEM test and then subsequently unloaded. The pouch cell with the encapsulation intact loaded in 3 point bending is shown in Figure 3(b).

Figure 3: (a) Simultaneous electrochemical-flexural testing experimental set-up;(b) A pouch cell undergoing a 3-point bend test; (c) research work flow of structural battery found in literature; (d) Simultaneous electro-mechanical testing

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Current collector selection

In this section, the current collector selection is justified based on the resistivity measurements and the tensile behaviour of the current collectors[10]. The tensile behaviour and resistivity measurements of various current collectors are summarized below.

Current collector tensile behaviour

Figure 4: Tensile stress-strain behaviour of different current collectors

The tensile stress-strain behaviour of various current collectors is shown in Figure 4 and the tensile strength and modulus are tabulated in Table 2. The CF-PVDF current collectors exhibit a higher tensile strength and tensile modulus compared to the CF-CNT current collectors.

Table 2 Tensile properties of various current collectors

Sample	Strength(MPa)	Young's Modulus(GPa)
1%CF-PVDF	1970.9	140.1
5%CF-PVDF	1649.1	104.5
CF-CNT-1c	1246.8	88.5
CF-CNT-2c	1172.9	89.9
CF-CNT-PVDF	1601.2	91.5

Current collector resistivity

The resistivities of various current collectors are tabulated in Table 3. Despite PVDF being an electrical insulator, the CF-PVDF current collectors exhibit a lower longitudinal (along the fibre direction) and through thickness resistivity compared to the CF-CNT samples. This might be because the CF-CNT current collectors do not have a uniform distribution of the electrically conductive CNTs through the thickness.

Table 3 Electrical resistivity of current collectors along the fibre (longitudinal direction) and the thickness direction

Sample label	Longitudinal resistivity (Ω mm)	Through thickness resistivity(Ω mm)
CF	0.021	48.092
1%CF-PVDF	0.032	22.593
5%CF-PVDF	0.041	24.505
CF-CNT-2c	0.057	38.254
CF-CNT-1c	0.053	46.939
CF-CNT-PVDF	0.070	75.211

Comparison of current collectors

Figure 5 Comparison of (a) Longitudinal resistivity; (b) through thickness resistivity and (c) Young's modulus across fabricated composite current collector samples

The various current collectors are compared in terms of longitudinal resistivity, through thickness resistivity and tensile modulus in Figure 5. The 1% CF-PVDF current collector exhibit the least resistivity and highest tensile modulus. However, since the various tows of the 1%CF-PVDF current collector samples were not well bonded to one another (Figure 10 in the appendix), it was difficult to fabricate pouch cells with the 1%CF-PVDF current collectors. Instead, 5% CF-PVDF current collectors were used to fabricate the structural battery pouch cells whose electrochemical performance is discussed in the next section.

3.2 Pouch cell electrochemical performance

The pouch cells fabricated were electrochemically tested as described in section 2.2 by charging and discharging between 1 and 2.5V at 0.1C and 0.2C charging rates. The voltage capacity graph of a single pouch cell at room temperature and at 60°C are shown in Figures 6(a) and (b), respectively. The capacity at room temperature is lower than the capacity at 60°C since the ionic conductivity of the PEO based solid electrolyte is sub-optimal at room temperature. The pouch cells' performance at 60°C shows reasonable repeatability as observed from the voltage-specific capacity graphs of three pouch cells in Figure 7, indicating a repeatable battery fabrication process. The capacity fading observed in the prototypes' performance at 60°C is similar to the PEO cells cycled at high temperature reported in literature [13].

Figure 6: Voltage-capacity behaviour of structural battery pouch cell of the configuration shown in Figure 2 at (a) 25 °C; (b) 60°C

Figure 7: The voltage capacity graphs for three pouch cell prototypes cycled at 60°C

3.3 Simultaneous electro-mechanical testing

Simultaneous Electro-Mechanical (SEM) testing of a pouch cell was carried out as described in section 2.3. The voltage specific capacity of the cell before loading is shown in Figure 8(a) by the blue curve. The cell was loaded to about 40N in three-point bending (as seen in Figure 3(b)) corresponding to 1mm cross head displacement as shown in Figure 8(b). The loading pin was held at the same position after loading the cell. The load decreased after the initial loading but was not recorded and therefore not reported here. Although the load is not constant, but the loading pin position is held stationary during the SEM test.

Since the test is carried out at room temperature, the capacity is lower and a higher charging rate is used to decrease the total testing time. The voltage decreases upon loading during charging as can be seen in the loaded box in Figure 8(a). This most likely is due to the decreased resistance upon loading due to better contact during the loading of the pouch cell. The cycle shown in orange in Figure 8(a) was charged during the application of the three-point bending (i.e. the orange curve between the loaded and unloaded boxes) The lower voltage observed in the charging phase of the cycle in orange is due to application of the mechanical load. Subsequently, the voltage is seen to increase upon unloading during the charging phase.

Figure 8: (a) Voltage vs specific capacity of cell before and after applying a bending load. The voltage decreases upon application of load most likely due to decreased resistance because of improved contact. The SEM test is conducted during the charging phase represented by the orange curve between the “loaded” and “unloaded” boxes. (b) Force-displacement graph during the application of load (i.e. “Loaded” box) in Figure 8(a).

Figure 9 shows the subsequent three cycles after the initial cycles plotted in Figure 8(a). The performance of the cell improved in the immediate cycle (grey plot in Figure 9) after the SEM test depicted in Figure 8(a) as evident from the increased capacity. This suggests that the pouch cell is in an improved state of contact (leading to decreased cell resistance) during the

1st (grey plot in Figure 9) and 2nd cycles (yellow plot in Figure 9) after SEM. However, by the third cycle (red plot in Figure 9) after the SEM test, the capacity of the cell returned to the pre-SEM level (blue plot). In conventional battery testing, these type of contact effects are avoided, and the best possible electrochemical performance is obtained by using a fixture shown in Figure 11 in the appendix. This demonstrates the need for simultaneous electro-mechanical testing of structural battery pouch cells since the effect of load on electrochemical performance is quantified and simultaneous multi-functionality is demonstrated. Structural battery research needs to progress from an isolated multi-functionality evaluation (Figure 3(c)) to simultaneous multi-functionality evaluation (Figure 3(d)) as discussed in this work for practical realization of structural batteries.

Figure 9 The comparison of the voltage vs specific capacity after the mechanical 3-point bending test.

The orange and blue curves are the same cycles from *Error! Reference source not found.*. The subsequent cycle displays an increase in charge and discharge capacity that decreases in the subsequent cycles suggesting that the improved contact that was established during loading relaxes with time returning back to the previous state (See 3rd cycle after load released (red curve) and cycle before mechanical load (blue curve)).

4 CONCLUSION

Carbon fibre based current collectors are used to develop PEO solid electrolyte based structural battery prototypes. The current collector with 5% PVDF solution was used to make the prototypes even though 1% PVDF samples exhibited the least resistivity and higher tensile properties since 1% CF PVDF current collectors are not suitable for making large pouch cell prototypes (as explained in section 3.1). The optimum amount of PVDF is indicated to lie between 1% and 5% CF-PVDF as observed from the measurements.

Pouch cells made with LFP and LTO electrodes with PEO solid electrolyte were successfully demonstrated to cycle electrochemically at room temperature and 60°C. These prototypes have been demonstrated to be fabricated with reasonable amount of repeatability as indicated in the performance of 3 pouch cells. Finally, a proposed Simultaneous Electro-Mechanical (SEM) flexural test has been performed. The battery could operate during and

after the test. The batteries exhibited higher capacities in the subsequent cycles mostly due to improved contact but eventually relaxed and returned to pre-SEM capacity.

Research and development of standards for these and similar simultaneous electromechanical tests and exploring alternate time-efficient methods to demonstrate simultaneous multi-functionality is necessary for the evaluation of structural batteries.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

The support of A*Star under Structural power for portable and electrified transportation; grant no. A20H3b0140 is gratefully acknowledged.

APPENDIX

A.1 Anode and cathode slurry preparation:

LFP + C : 88:5 mass ratio of LFP powder and Carbon (C65) Black Powder are mixed using a pestle and mortar for cathode.

- (a) 1 g of LFP + C mixed above
- (b) 1.2 g of DMF (N, N Dimethylformamide) solvent
- (c) 4.5 g of PEO10-LiTFSI-DMF solution
- (d) 4 g of 5% PVDF-DMF solution (a 5:95 mass ratio of PVDF-DMF solution)
- (e) 2 g of 0.4% Single Walled Carbon Nanotube (SWCNT) 2% PVDF in NMP (N-Methyl pyrrolidone)

The above ingredients are added in glass bottle as per the weights one by one and centrifuged at 2000rpm for two minutes after the addition of each component from (b) to ensure uniformity of the slurry.

For the anode, LTO + C: 90:5 mass ratio of LTO powder and Carbon (C65) Black Powder is mixed with a pestle and mortar and replaces the LFP+C in the above recipe

A.2 PEO₁₀-LiTFSI solid electrolyte preparation:

Add 1 g of LiTFSI (Lithium bis(trifluoromethanesulfonyl)imide) and 1.533 g of PEO(poly(ethylene) oxide) in glass bottle inside a glovebox to avoid moisture absorption. Add DMF(Dimethylformamide) solvent such that the total solid content (PEO + LiTFSI) is 10% of the total mass after adding DMF. Place a stirrer bar and place in oil bath at 80°C and stir at 500 rpm for 12 hours to prepare the electrolyte.

Figure 10: 1% CF-PVDF fabricated sample with disconnected individual tows- makes it difficult to assemble cells

Figure 11: Fixture used in conventional pouch cell testing to ensure proper contact within the cell and ensure the best battery performance

REFERENCES

- [1] L.E. Asp, E.S. Greenhalgh, Structural power composites, *Compos. Sci. Technol.* 101 (2014) 41–61. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compscitech.2014.06.020>.
- [2] D. Carlstedt, L.E. Asp, Performance analysis framework for structural battery composites in electric vehicles, *Compos. Part B Eng.* 186 (2020) 107822. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compositesb.2020.107822>.
- [3] Q. Jiang, A. Beutl, H. Kühnelt, A. Bismarck, Structural composite batteries made from carbon fibre reinforced electrodes / polymer gel electrolyte prepregs, *Compos. Sci. Technol.* 244 (2023) 110312. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compscitech.2023.110312>.
- [4] G.J.H. Lim, R. Chua, J.J. Koh, K.K. Chan, E.J.J. Tang, V. Teh, M. Srinivasan, Structural and conformable designs for aqueous multifunctional batteries, *Mater. Today Energy* 33 (2023) 101255. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1016/j.mtener.2023.101255>.
- [5] L.E. Asp, K. Bouton, D. Carlstedt, S. Duan, R. Harnden, W. Johannisson, M. Johansen, M.K.G. Johansson, G. Lindbergh, F. Liu, K. Peuvot, L.M. Schneider, J. Xu, D. Zenkert, A Structural Battery and its Multifunctional Performance, *Adv. Energy Sustain. Res.* 2 (2021) 2000093. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1002/aesr.202000093>.
- [6] R. Chaudhary, J. Xu, Z. Xia, L.E. Asp, Unveiling the Multifunctional Carbon Fiber Structural Battery, *Adv. Mater.* 36 (2024) 2409725. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1002/adma.202409725>.
- [7] K. Bouton, L. Schneider, D. Zenkert, G. Lindbergh, A structural battery with carbon fibre electrodes balancing multifunctional performance, *Compos. Sci. Technol.* 256 (2024) 110728. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compscitech.2024.110728>.
- [8] R. Tavano, M. Spagnol, N. Al-Ramahi, R. Joffe, J. Xu, L.E. Asp, Mechanical characterisation of a structural battery electrolyte, *Polymer (Guildf)*. 312 (2024) 127646. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1016/j.polymer.2024.127646>.
- [9] N. Ding, S.W. Chien, T.L.D. Tam, X. Li, G. Wu, W.J. Lee, S.Y. Chiam, Y.S. Meng, D.W.H. Fam, Revealing Phase Transitions in Poly(Ethylene Oxide)-Based Electrolyte for Room-Temperature Solid-State Batteries, *Adv. Energy Mater.* 14 (2024) 2402986. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1002/aenm.202402986>.
- [10] K. Raju, S. Dong, T.-E. Tay, Developing Carbon Fibre Composite Current Collectors for Structural Battery Applications, (2024). <https://doi.org/10.1115/IMECE2024-146111>.
- [11] K.K. Chan, G.J.H. Lim, N.A.A. Sutrisnoh, K. Raju, M. Srinivasan, Toward a Safe and High Performance Quasi-Solid-State Structural Battery, *ACS Appl. Energy Mater.* 7 (2024) 9098–9109. <https://doi.org/10.1021/acsaem.4c00981>.
- [12] K. Raju, T.-E. Tay, V.B.C. Tan, Multi-functional performance evaluation of carbon fibre structural battery composite prototypes with flexural mechanical loading, in: 21st Eur. Conf. Compos. Mater., The European Society for Composite Materials (ESCM) and the Ecole Centrale de Nantes., Nantes, 2024: p. Volume 6: 355-362. <https://doi.org/10.60691/yj56-np80>.
- [13] G. Homann, L. Stolz, J. Nair, I.C. Laskovic, M. Winter, J. Kasnatscheew, Poly(Ethylene Oxide)-based Electrolyte for Solid-State-Lithium-Batteries with High Voltage Positive Electrodes: Evaluating the Role of Electrolyte Oxidation in Rapid Cell Failure, *Sci. Rep.* 10 (2020) 4390. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-020-61373-9>.